

Case description

Scale of intervention

- Individual
- Household/building
- Neighbourhood
- City
- Region
- Other:

Type of intervention

- Policy/program
- (Re)development
- Infrastructure
- Project
- Behavioural
- Other:

Map the activities that need to be carried out

Spatial Justice Concerns

- Allocating budget and resources to areas/groups that need the most
- Including citizens and local initiatives and businesses in the process
- Make sure the intervention fulfills the needs and preferences of marginalised groups
- Other: _____